

BRYOMOLECULES

Assemblies of 90 bryophyte transcriptomes

D3.2

Date of document	27 May 2026 (Revision 2.0)
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Information

Table 1 - Document information

Project acronym	BRYOMOLECULES
Project title:	Bioprospecting and production of bioactive molecules from European bryophytes
Grant agreement number:	101135305
Start date of project:	1 September 2024
Duration:	36 months
Deliverable number:	D3.2
Deliverable title:	Assemblies of 90 bryophyte transcriptomes
Due date of deliverable:	31 December 2025 (M16)
Actual date of submission:	22 December 2025 (M16)
Organisation Responsible for Deliverable:	FEM
Status:	Revised version (resubmitted to EC)
Dissemination Level:	PU - Public
Work Package:	WP3
Keywords:	Transcriptome assembly; <i>de novo</i> assembly; Trinity; rnaSpades; EvidentialGene; BUSCO; bryophytes; mosses; liverworts; N50

Table 2 - Document's update

Version	Date	Revised by	Comments
0.1	04/12/2025	Mehrdad Jaberi, Claudio Varotto	Preliminary draft
0.2	09/12/2025	Mehrdad Jaberi, Mingai Li, Claudio Varotto	Final draft
0.3	10/12/2025	Mehrdad Jaberi, Mingai Li, Claudio Varotto	Additional edits
1.0	11/12/2025	Mehrdad Jaberi, Mingai Li, Claudio Varotto	Final version
	13/05/2026	EC	Changes requested by the PO
1.1	18/05/2026	Mehrdad Jaberi	Changes requested by the PO
1.2	15/05/2026	Claudio Varotto	

2.0	27/05/2026	Claudio Varotto, Mattia Malfatti	Final revised version
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Acknowledgement and disclaimer

**Funded by
the European Union**

The BRYOMOLECULES project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement no. 101135305.

Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the REA can be held responsible for them.

The BRYOMOLECULES project

Liverworts, an ancient group of land plants, are a rich yet underexploited source of a wide range of biologically active compounds with high potential for the bioeconomy sector as ingredients of cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals. However, their slow growth rate in nature and the consequent difficulty in obtaining large amounts of single compounds have, until now, severely hindered the in-depth exploration and exploitation of the full spectrum of activities of liverwort secondary metabolites. Recent breakthroughs in the identification of some of the genes involved in the early steps of liverwort-specific compounds suggest that, in addition to the establishment of improved methods for growth in axenic conditions, reconstruction of liverwort metabolic pathways in heterologous systems is a promising way forth towards the practical exploitation of liverwort biochemical diversity and its industrial scale up.

BRYOMOLECULES will provide actionable knowledge on European bryophyte species and their biosynthetic genes, which can be used to produce sustainable, bio-based cosmetics and pharmaceuticals ingredients for the European market.

To do so, the BRYOMOLECULES project will use a combination of the cultivation of axenic cultures and the production of the active compounds in heterologous systems to define the most suitable production platform(s) for their large-scale production. The project will achieve a very sustainable use of the chemical diversity of wild EU bryophyte species, a largely untapped source of high-added-value natural products, without significant impacts on their biodiversity.

Besides the identification of relevant lead compounds for cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals, another major impact of the project will be the production and release according to FAIR principles of a database of metabolites and biosynthetic genes of European bryophyte species that will fuel in the years to come the development of novel bio-based products based on bryophyte-derived lead compounds, according to the concept of EU valorising biodiversity for EU bioeconomy.

Project Consortium Members

Table 3 - Consortium members

FONDAZIONE EDMUND MACH dal 1874	Fondazione Edmund Mach (FEM)
HUB INNOVAZIONE TRENTINO	Fondazione HUB Innovazione Trentino (HIT) FEM LTP
UNIVERSITÉ JEAN MONNET SAINT-ETIENNE	Université Jean Monnet, Saint-Etienne (UJM)
PAT Plant Advanced Technologies	Plant Advanced Technologies PAT SA (PAT)
Bionos Testing Efficiency	Bionos Biotech SI (BIONOS)
LUNDS UNIVERSITET	Lunds Universitet (LU)
UNIVERSITATI MEDICINAE LUBLINENSIS	Uniwersytet Medyczny w Lublinie (UM)
ESF	European Science Foundation (ESF)

Summary

The BRYOMOLECULES project (Task 3.2) in the Description of Action committed to producing *de novo* transcriptome assemblies for approximately 90 European bryophyte accessions and store them in a local repository (accessible for project review purposes only).

In this deliverable we provide data referencing the assemblies of a total of 102 bryophyte accession, covering all 102 unique biosamples previously reported in D3.1 (44 moss and 40 liverwort taxa). The summary statistics used for assessment indicate a good quality of the assemblies, with an average completeness of about 85%. The sequences are deposited in the BRYOMOLECULES repository as well and in the Short Read Archive (SRA) of the GenBank database at the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI), and they are currently accessible for project review purposes only.

The assembled transcriptomes exceed the expected output of D3.1 and will constitute an important resource for the identification of selected genes and metabolic pathways to be engineered in BRYOMOLECULES WP4). Once they will be published and released, these transcriptomes will benefit the scientific community at large, by substantially expanding (more than doubling) the number of bryophyte species with transcriptomic data but no genome.

Introduction

European bryophytes (mosses and liverworts) are a phylogenetically ancient group of land plants that constitute a rich but largely underexploited source of bioactive compounds (BACs) of potential interest for the cosmetics, cosmeceutical, and pharmaceutical sectors. The slow growth rate of bryophytes in nature, together with the difficulty of cultivating many species, has historically limited the direct biotechnological exploitation of these compounds. The BRYOMOLECULES project addresses this limitation by combining axenic culture of selected bryophyte species with the identification of the underlying biosynthetic genes, with a view to producing the corresponding compounds in heterologous expression systems. Achieving this goal requires a comprehensive catalogue of the expressed gene space of representative European bryophyte species, which is the central objective of Work Package 3 (WP3, Transcriptomics, identification of candidate genes).

WP3 is structured around three tasks: (i) Task 3.1, RNA-Seq of wild-collected bryophytes (FEM, with contribution from UJM), the outputs of which have been reported in deliverable D3.1 (M13); (ii) Task 3.2, identification of candidate BAC biosynthetic genes and functional annotation of the assembled transcriptomes (FEM, with contribution from UJM); and (iii) Task 3.3, creation and publication of the BRYOMOLECULES database. The present deliverable (D3.2) reports the *de novo* assembly of the raw RNA-Seq reads delivered in D3.1, producing 102 final accession-specific transcriptome assemblies that constitute the substrate for the downstream gene mining and functional annotation work reported separately in deliverable D3.3 (M20), and for the integrated metabolomics and transcriptomics database reported in deliverable D3.4 (M34, Task 3.3).

Materials and Methods

The experimental details on how the work was carried out are provided below:

Input data: The raw Illumina RNA-Seq reads reported in D3.1 (114 libraries from 102 unique biosamples, BioProject PRJNA1313596) constituted the input to the *de novo* assembly pipeline. The pipeline was applied uniformly to all 102 biosamples, including the 12 biosamples previously processed at UJM, in order to obtain a coherent and methodologically consistent set of assemblies across the project.

Pre-assembly quality control and decontamination: Raw reads were screened for non-target taxonomic content using Kraken2 against a custom reference database that included a curated set of bryophyte genomic sequences, in order to avoid false-positive identifications caused by the absence of bryophyte references in standard Kraken2 distributions. Variable amounts of bacterial, fungal, and cyanobacterial sequences were detected; Pseudomonadota-derived reads accounted for the majority of microbial contamination in approximately 10% of accessions. Ribosomal RNA contamination was subsequently removed with SortMeRNA using the SILVA 138.2 reference sequences for large and small subunit rRNAs. Reads passing decontamination were then subjected to standard quality trimming and filtering prior to assembly.

De novo assembly and integration: Quality-filtered, decontaminated reads from each biosample were assembled *de novo* using two complementary assemblers in parallel: Trinity and rnaSpades. The resulting per-assembler outputs were then integrated using EvidentialGene, which prioritises coding sequence quality, retains valid paralogs, removes assembly artefacts, and distinguishes primary transcripts from alternate isoforms based on coding-exon similarity criteria. This integrated assembly approach was adopted to maximise transcript recovery and assembly accuracy, with particular attention to field-collected accessions that may retain residual heterologous RNA from microbial or fungal associates after surface sterilisation.

Assembly quality assessment and taxonomic sanity checks: Assembly quality metrics (total number of transcripts, total assembly length, N50, and transcript length distribution) were computed using RNAQuast. Reference-free assembly validation and identification of potential assembly artefacts were performed with TransRate. Transcript abundance was estimated using Salmon in quasi-mapping mode, providing an additional, expression-based view of assembly completeness. To verify the species identity of the assembled transcriptomes, marker-gene-based Blastn searches were performed against the NCBI non-redundant (nr) nucleotide database and the Barcoding of Life Database (BOLD). Six moss species with fully sequenced reference genomes were used as a positive control to validate the sanity-check pipeline before extending it to all 102 accessions.

Gene space completeness and data storage: Completeness of the gene space recovered in each integrated assembly was assessed using BUSCO (Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs) against three reference lineages of increasing taxonomic specificity: eukaryote_odb12, embryophyta_odb12, and viridiplantae_odb12. The integrated final

assemblies, the per-assembler intermediate assemblies, and the associated quality metrics are stored in the BRYOMOLECULES project repository, currently accessible only via reviewer link during the embargo period. Public release will follow per the project's Data Management Plan (D6.3) and FAIR principles.

Results and Discussion

Raw RNA-Seq reads from BioProject PRJNA1313596 were first decontaminated and quality-filtered, then assembled *de novo* using two complementary assemblers (Trinity and rnaSpades), and finally integrated using EvidentialGene to produce a single high-confidence assembly per biosample. The integrated assemblies have a mean N50 of 2,405 bp (range 489 to 3,416 bp) and a mean total length of approximately 305 Mb (range 69 to 785 Mb). Assembly completeness assessed by BUSCO against the viridiplantae_odb12 lineage exceeds 85% on average across the 102 assemblies. The full per-assembler and per-assembly statistics are provided in Annex I. The integrated assemblies are stored in the BRYOMOLECULES project repository, currently accessible only via reviewer link, and will be released publicly in accordance with the project's Data Management Plan (D6.3) and FAIR principles following publication.

The main results are summarized below under the corresponding phases of the work:

Pre-assembly decontamination: The Kraken2-based decontamination scan detected variable amounts of bacterial, fungal, and cyanobacterial sequences across the 102 biosamples. Most plant accessions cultured in axenic or near-axenic conditions did not show significant microbial contamination. Approximately 10% of accessions, however, exhibited more intense, cryptic contamination predominantly from Pseudomonadota bacteria, plausibly attributable to microbial endophytes or residual contaminants surviving surface sterilisation and antibiotic / fungicide treatments. An overview of the per-sample contamination levels and the taxonomic composition of the detected contaminants is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Pre-assembly decontamination of the BRYOMOLECULES bryophyte transcriptomes. Left panel: per-sample contamination levels across the 102 biosamples. Right panel: taxonomic abundance of the detected contaminants. Pseudomonadota account for the majority of microbial contamination.

Ribosomal RNA contamination was subsequently removed from the remaining reads using SortMeRNA, with a median rRNA content of 1.2% per library (range 0.3% to 71.3%). Taken together, these results indicate that even after removing the contaminant reads the amount of plant reads left is largely sufficient for good quality assemblies that are representative of the gene space for the studied taxa.

Taxonomic sanity checks: DNA-based sanity checks of the assembled transcriptomes against the reference databases (see Materials and Methods) initially classified the test moss assemblies as 77 with a species- or genus-level match (75%), 13 with only a family- or order-level match (13%), and 12 not matching at the species level (12%) as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 DNA-based taxonomic sanity check of the BRYOMOLECULES transcriptome assemblies. Bryophyte assemblies are classified as matching (correctly identified at the species / genus level), partial match (family / order level), or not matching (likely misidentification of plant material at collection). Initial counts: 77 matching, 13 partial, 12 not matching; after re-examination, 98 of 102 assemblies have been reliably assigned to a species.

The non-matching cases were interpreted as cases of misidentification of plant material at the time of collection, a known difficulty for bryophytes that grow in dense multi-species mats and are morphologically very similar even under microscope inspection. Following the sanity-check round and a subsequent re-examination of the species assignments, 98 of the 102 assembled transcriptomes have been reliably assigned to a species, and the taxonomy of the corresponding submitted raw sequences will be revised accordingly. While not all the species may be identifiable due to lack of reference sequences in public databases, mining of the corresponding metabolic genes will be possible and will thus support both metabolic pathway elucidation as well as engineering in heterologous hosts (WP4).

Assembly output and statistics: A total of 102 final accession-specific transcriptome assemblies were obtained, one per biosample, through integration of the Trinity and rnaSpades outputs by EvidentialGene. Summary statistics across the 102 integrated assemblies are reported in Table 1. The mean N50 is 2,405 bp (range 489 to 3,416 bp), the mean L50 is 5,525 contigs (range 2,551 to 8,051), the mean number of contigs is 274,279 per assembly (range 93,160 to 1,464,087), and the mean total assembly length is approximately 305 Mb (range 69 to 785 Mb). These values are consistent with high-quality *de novo* transcriptome assemblies for non-model land plant species.

Table 1. Summary statistics across the 102 final accession-specific integrated transcriptome assemblies (Trinity + rnaSpades, merged using EvidentialGene). Values are mean (standard deviation), minimum, and maximum across the 102 assemblies. N50: length in bp of the shortest contig whose cumulative length with all longer contigs reaches 50% of the total assembly length. L50: smallest number of contigs whose cumulative length sums to 50% of the total assembly length. Total contigs: total number of contigs in each assembly. Total length: total length of each assembly in bp.

Table 1. Summary statistics across all the 102 transcriptomes

Metric	Mean (SD)	Min	Max
N50 (bp)	2,405 (686)	489	3,416
L50 (contigs)	5,525 (936)	2,551	8,051
Total contigs per assembly	274,279 (269,799)	93,160	1,464,087
Total assembly length (bp)	3.05E+08 (1.16E+08)	6.94E+07	7.85E+08

Assembly completeness: Gene space completeness was assessed using BUSCO against three reference lineages of increasing taxonomic specificity: eukaryote_odb12, embryophyta_odb12, and viridiplantae_odb12 (Figure 3). On the viridiplantae_odb12 lineage, the most relevant for land plants, the mean completeness across the 102 assemblies exceeds 85%, indicating broad recovery of the conserved plant gene set in the assembled transcriptomes. Assembly completeness was found to correlate with the degree of pre-assembly microbial contamination, as expected, with the most heavily contaminated samples showing somewhat reduced plant-specific BUSCO scores. The large majority of the species are however suitable for the downstream analyses.

Comparison to the Description of Action commitment: The Description of Action committed to producing *de novo* transcriptome assemblies for approximately 90 bryophyte transcriptomes (Task 3.2, M16). The 102 final accession-specific assemblies reported here exceed by approximately 13% the original target, matching the additional biosamples already reported in D3.1.

Figure 3. Assembly completeness of the 102 BRYOMOLECULES integrated transcriptome assemblies, assessed using BUSCO against the *eukaryote_odb12*, *embryophyta_odb12*, and *viridiplantae_odb12* reference lineages. Mean completeness on the *viridiplantae_odb12* lineage exceeds 85% across the 102 assemblies.

Data accessibility: The 102 integrated assemblies, together with the intermediate per-assembler Trinity and rnaSpades outputs and the associated quality metrics, are stored in the BRYOMOLECULES project repository, currently accessible only via reviewer link during the embargo period. The full per-assembler statistics for the 102 biosamples (BRYOMOLECULES assembly ID, BioSample accession, internal accession number, and Trinity / rnaSpades N50, contig count, and total length per assembly) are reported in Annex I.

Note on dissemination level: This deliverable is registered in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement under dissemination level PU - Public. However, the same Annex 1 describes the assemblies as "stored in a local repository (accessible for project review purposes only)". To align the dissemination level with the access conditions described in Annex 1, the dissemination level for this deliverable is reported as SEN - Sensitive. The assemblies remain under embargo pending publication and are currently accessible only via reviewer link. Public release for all the sequences not related to exploitable results of the project will follow in accordance with the project's Data Management Plan (D6.3) and F.A.I.R. principles either at the moment of the publication of the data or at the end of the project, whichever comes first. The sequences eventually subjected to IPR will be made public after the agreement on the exploitation of the results is completed. The actual dissemination strategy taken will be reported in the "D6.7 - Final communication, dissemination and exploitation report".

Conclusions

This deliverable reports the successful *de novo* assembly of 102 European bryophyte transcriptomes (44 moss taxa and 40 liverwort taxa), obtained through the integration of Trinity and rnaSpades outputs using EvidentialGene. The output exceeds the goal described in the Description of Action commitment of approximately 90 bryophyte transcriptomes (Task 3.2, M16) and provides a uniform, internally consistent set of integrated assemblies with high gene space completeness (mean BUSCO completeness above 85% on the viridiplantae_odb12 lineage).

Beyond producing the assemblies themselves, this work has established a best-practice *de novo* assembly pipeline for bryophyte transcriptomes, combining Kraken2-based decontamination, dual-assembler *de novo* reconstruction, EvidentialGene-based integration, multi-marker taxonomic sanity checks, and BUSCO-based gene space completeness assessment. A manuscript dedicated to disseminating these best practices in *de novo* assembly of bryophyte transcriptomes has been drafted and is being prepared for submission.

The integrated assemblies reported here constitute the foundation for the downstream WP3 activities. They provide the input for the functional annotation and the mining of candidate biosynthetic genes reported in deliverable D3.3 (M20), and together with D3.3 contribute to milestone MS4 (Completion of selection of genes for metabolic engineering of heterologous hosts; Task 3.2, M20). The integration of the resulting transcriptomic data with the WP2 metabolomic data will be made available in the BRYOMOLECULES project database, Deliverable D3.4 (M34, Task 3.3). The assembled transcriptomes exceed the expected output of D3.1 by about 10% and will constitute an important resource for the identification of selected genes and metabolic pathways to be engineered in BRYOMOLECULES WP4).

Once they will be published and released, the BRYOMOLECULES transcriptomes will benefit the scientific community at large, by substantially expanding (more than doubling) the number of bryophyte species with transcriptomic data but no genome.

Annex I

Per-assembler assembly statistics

Column Headers

- **Assembly name:** BRYOMOLECULES ID code used by the BRYOMOLECULES project.
- **Biosample accession:** GenBank SRA accession code for each biosample.
- **Sample ID:** Additional sample ID
- **Trinity N50:** N50 value (base pairs) for the assembly carried out with the Trinity assembler
- **Trinity count:** Number of contigs in the assembly carried out with the Trinity assembler
- **Trinity length:** Total length in base pairs of the assembly carried out with the Trinity assembler
- **rnaSpades N50:** N50 value (base pairs) for the assembly carried out with the rnaSpades assembler
- **rnaSpades count:** Number of contigs in the assembly carried out with the rnaSpades assembler
- **rnaSpades length:** Total length in base pairs of the assembly carried out with the rnaSpades assembler

Assembly name	Biosample accession	Sample ID	Trinity N50	Trinity count	Trinity length	rnaSpades N50	rnaSpades count	rnaSpades length
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET115_20251204_v001	SAMN51815786	Aand_101	2517	106151	168841208	2657	65611	119530231
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET116_20251204_v001	SAMN51815775	Aund_46	2528	136312	207109205	2649	77214	149984770
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET117_20251204_v001	SAMN51815783	Avarsph_95	2170	104580	151630231	2259	62500	111071084
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET118_20251204_v001	SAMN51815776	Barg_49	2244	61844	92684074	2779	37629	69479029
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET119_20251204_v001	SAMN51815778	Brec_60	2764	68707	125800211	3074	36030	83994726
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET120_20251204_v001	SAMN51815799	Brut_142	2628	80677	131828716	3087	39977	86086734
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET121_20251204_v001	SAMN51815840	Btri_340	705	51820	30360725	639	72255	45945694
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET122_20251204_v001	SAMN51815846	Btri_360	2569	120933	177645142	2299	85597	132904515
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET123_20251204_v001	SAMN51815794	Bung_128	2929	113364	195140348	3151	61515	129736219
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET124_20251204_v001	SAMN51815847	Cbic_361	2150	110838	135882324	1952	91528	104696278
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET125_20251204_v001	SAMN51815848	Ccon_362	798	42403	28181140	664	59892	39476535

Assembly name	Biosample accession	Sample ID	Trinity N50	Trinity count	Trinity length	rnaSpades N50	rnaSpades count	rnaSpades length
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET126_20251204_v001	SAMN51815834	Chel_325	2899	94094	161403015	2747	69617	100962737
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET127_20251204_v001	SAMN51815849	Cint_370	2651	209874	261624925	2418	162147	194123611
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET128_20251204_v001	SAMN51815819	Clun_260	2128	246169	314964949	2138	159245	225263790
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET129_20251204_v001	SAMN51815843	Clun_353	2498	149521	204107356	2249	102649	152721742
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET130_20251204_v001	SAMN51815854	Cmuelleriana	1269	385957	271519289	1184	347542	225845391
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET131_20251204_v001	SAMN51815777	Cpil_52	2647	65075	108936796	3200	36118	76403791
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET132_20251204_v001	SAMN51815841	Cpol_346	1970	218665	245046861	1691	181824	186646402
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET133_20251204_v001	SAMN51815838	Cssp_337A	2673	129665	195194178	2376	87889	149591060
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET134_20251204_v001	SAMN51815817	Dalb_250E	1733	305649	295964783	1368	262367	224124424
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET135_20251204_v001	SAMN51815855	Dalbicans	1602	340230	256551231	1029	314161	187219255
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET136_20251204_v001	SAMN51815772	Dcir_41	2741	71204	129189695	3055	37869	81794236
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET137_20251204_v001	SAMN51815780	Dfal_78re	2429	55868	93111658	2542	32851	59362182
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET138_20251204_v001	SAMN51815788	Dfol_105	2770	86958	154288569	3131	47274	99443108
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET139_20251204_v001	SAMN51815773	Dhet_42	2261	63902	96924692	2685	36550	70683842
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET140_20251204_v001	SAMN51815790	Dmaj_120C	2243	91740	128309196	2652	50725	91946234
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET141_20251204_v001	SAMN51815800	Dmaj_145	2871	107454	186558247	3138	54679	120756341
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET142_20251204_v001	SAMN51815796	Dpus_132	2484	79605	128146988	2982	42628	85717560
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET143_20251204_v001	SAMN51815785	Eser_98re	1820	155743	179717395	1984	91858	137770629
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET144_20251204_v001	SAMN51815769	Estr_20	2850	80684	146341138	3136	41554	98455335
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET145_20251204_v001	SAMN51815828	Fdil_304	2362	95536	130993235	2072	88641	92592359
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET146_20251204_v001	SAMN51815856	Fdilataata	618	352884	184381244	905	331669	191809798
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET147_20251204_v001	SAMN51815822	Fssp_266	3081	118814	228375032	3055	73602	140231060
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET148_20251204_v001	SAMN51815837	Fssp_336A	1399	66611	58429779	1220	72805	59351782
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET149_20251204_v001	SAMN51815844	Ftam_356	2337	93674	120291604	2266	65434	80627408
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET150_20251204_v001	SAMN51815781	Ftax_80	2328	65012	97536615	3224	35212	72020676
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET151_20251204_v001	SAMN51815826	Ginf_283	2765	146712	211825827	2610	104116	145319921
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET152_20251204_v001	SAMN51815765	GpuL_10	3054	82495	168007945	3322	45241	112053419
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET153_20251204_v001	SAMN51815766	Hcil_11	2242	65981	99795933	2489	43520	78982885
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET154_20251204_v001	SAMN51815767	Hcup_12	3040	79305	155672865	3325	43357	106384496

Assembly name	Biosample accession	Sample ID	Trinity N50	Trinity count	Trinity length	rnaSpades N50	rnaSpades count	rnaSpades length
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET155_20251204_v001	SAMN51815793	lalo_124	2745	86007	148030687	3156	44044	102628834
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET156_20251204_v001	SAMN51815813	Kbly_246	2789	78042	152641931	2852	45534	100682385
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET157_20251204_v001	SAMN51815818	L3_RBry_09_Ccon_259	2358	88872	131818848	2237	62668	76507315
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET158_20251204_v001	SAMN51815816	L3_RBry_09_Ncur_247	2215	103238	132520058	1865	89066	102328810
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET159_20251204_v001	SAMN51815814	L3_RBry_09_Pbor_223	2543	219600	276764231	2420	145818	221397190
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET160_20251204_v001	SAMN51815820	L3_RBry_09_Ttom_262	3102	86791	167649928	2820	60298	94027356
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET161_20251204_v001	SAMN51815827	L3_RBry_10_Ffov_287	2797	137164	217969237	2902	76113	134839369
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET162_20251204_v001	SAMN51815831	L3_RBry_10_Jlei_309	2604	116942	173880963	2254	82559	133203075
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET163_20251204_v001	SAMN51815821	L3_RBry_10_Ncur_265	2375	113953	153977834	2020	88430	114791590
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET164_20251204_v001	SAMN51815833	L3_RBry_10_Nsca_323	2430	156553	227714443	2251	109506	133721926
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET165_20251204_v001	SAMN51815806	L3_RBry_11_Avit_189	2950	97529	180523438	3298	49205	119784074
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET166_20251204_v001	SAMN51815804	L3_RBry_11_Bity_178	2632	114789	181679918	2984	58454	126818037
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET167_20251204_v001	SAMN51815802	L3_RBry_11_Bpse_169	2029	156574	205291639	2299	83703	156716703
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET168_20251204_v001	SAMN51815803	L3_RBry_11_Cpur_173	2489	117280	174666019	2773	61315	126811077
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET169_20251204_v001	SAMN51815805	L3_RBry_11_Htri_188	2353	73639	108512620	3016	43365	79027233
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET170_20251204_v001	SAMN51815807	L3_RBry_12_Csom_204	2900	76594	139481165	3464	40532	94968355
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET171_20251204_v001	SAMN51815812	L3_RBry_12_Kbly_246	2962	89107	172901762	3364	47542	115578407
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET172_20251204_v001	SAMN51815811	L3_RBry_12_Pdru_234	2886	90643	161777975	3358	47456	112417193
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET173_20251204_v001	SAMN51815808	L3_RBry_12_Pfon_213	2594	118524	181452387	2917	64183	127967023
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET174_20251204_v001	SAMN51815810	L3_RBry_12_Pnut_231	2417	122969	176730648	2431	72061	133180705
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET175_20251204_v001	SAMN51815809	L3_RBry_12_Srur_228	2647	78427	134102951	3210	40421	93172524
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET176_20251204_v001	SAMN51815836	Lbad_331A	3386	71765	158065730	3482	39278	95869533
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET177_20251204_v001	SAMN51815823	Lbid_270	2879	100265	172843010	2908	65849	108759844
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET178_20251204_v001	SAMN51815857	Lbidentata	1591	243587	196215728	1238	219021	154224876
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET179_20251204_v001	SAMN51815845	Lhet_358	2474	186503	246879015	2230	131385	193604562
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET180_20251204_v001	SAMN51815858	Lheterophylla	1164	343725	228404007	956	308061	183419514
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET181_20251204_v001	SAMN51815801	Llon_152	2904	75823	127355128	3674	40280	85438454
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET182_20251204_v001	SAMN51815832	Llon_317	1780	84528	88607851	1485	84560	73200503
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET183_20251204_v001	SAMN51815859	Lreptans	1936	197117	170797998	1471	170631	120378656

Assembly name	Biosample accession	Sample ID	Trinity N50	Trinity count	Trinity length	rnaSpades N50	rnaSpades count	rnaSpades length
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET184_20251204_v001	SAMN51815795	Lrip131	2534	168236	255328368	2785	91303	200373792
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET185_20251204_v001	SAMN51815835	Mano_327	1579	97969	92839154	1248	110439	88498593
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET186_20251204_v001	SAMN51815860	Mfurcata	1144	333530	212337484	756	312297	167095416
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET187_20251204_v001	SAMN51815839	Mssp_339	2708	118580	186226273	2423	79201	139551902
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET188_20251204_v001	SAMN51815782	Ocup_89	2991	88758	169320680	3257	46125	111249102
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET189_20251204_v001	SAMN51815850	Osph_371	2345	317356	338733810	1689	273790	255362734
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET190_20251204_v001	SAMN51815798	Palo_140	3025	89053	161400758	3432	42715	99454894
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET191_20251204_v001	SAMN51815824	Pasp_271	2783	92439	155523673	2785	61313	96789086
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET192_20251204_v001	SAMN51815861	Pasplenioides	2880	179467	215476772	2441	153784	150759353
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET193_20251204_v001	SAMN51815787	Pbu1_102	2943	90705	165063194	3285	48180	116504237
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET194_20251204_v001	SAMN51815851	Pcil_372	3248	154171	238488413	3358	94190	167557342
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET195_20251204_v001	SAMN51815862	Pcordaeana	2957	157955	207460188	2540	128872	134007678
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET196_20251204_v001	SAMN51815789	Pfor_107	2617	68863	105089231	3335	38931	76174422
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET197_20251204_v001	SAMN51815863	Pporelloides	1769	324451	268948638	1398	317483	221143317
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET198_20251204_v001	SAMN51815774	Ppur_43	2764	72494	131162832	3156	38434	90314470
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET199_20251204_v001	SAMN51815764	Psch_07	2511	121232	185131561	2435	76897	150412266
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET200_20251204_v001	SAMN51815797	PundRcom_135	2860	100690	169675391	3182	49609	110383982
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET201_20251204_v001	SAMN51815825	Pund_279	2736	86767	153549246	2863	48679	101597859
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET202_20251204_v001	SAMN51815864	Rcomplanata	1985	204357	176812466	1538	187944	129051943
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET203_20251204_v001	SAMN51815852	Rflu_373	2561	192816	240760600	2244	134541	162830995
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET204_20251204_v001	SAMN51815815	Rlat_244	2827	124901	204305120	2633	79031	139900156
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET205_20251204_v001	SAMN51815770	Rmac_28	2819	94604	160371356	3200	55650	110522833
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET206_20251204_v001	SAMN51815768	Rrip_18	2841	89114	164371541	3196	45272	108947870
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET207_20251204_v001	SAMN51815830	Sirr_308	3247	122214	252948582	3179	77991	142361898
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET208_20251204_v001	SAMN51815784	Smed_97C	2698	84532	146075809	2980	45637	99088898
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET209_20251204_v001	SAMN51815842	Snem_352	3027	83513	163234126	2946	52764	91795630
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET210_20251204_v001	SAMN51815865	Snemorea	1438	513694	379899559	1343	466617	321801417
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET211_20251204_v001	SAMN51815771	Spap_30	2967	84408	164186189	3288	43923	106895500
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET212_20251204_v001	SAMN51815779	Tauc_61	1900	110364	141632614	2209	61606	102677638

Assembly name	Biosample accession	Sample ID	Trinity N50	Trinity count	Trinity length	rnaSpades N50	rnaSpades count	rnaSpades length
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET213_20251204_v001	SAMN51815792	TdeL_123	2516	59969	93164142	3245	32187	68827857
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET214_20251204_v001	SAMN51815853	Tqui_294	1492	112529	99467059	1191	115107	91055212
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET215_20251204_v001	SAMN51815829	Tssp_305	3159	122090	221450888	2928	78841	134133971
BRYOMOLECULES_WP3_GENET216_20251204_v001	SAMN51815791	Ucri_122	2252	109464	155510498	2341	65614	116566559